

COMPARISON, CHARACTERIZATION AND VALIDATION OF DIFFERENT DNA EXTRACTION PROCEDURES FOR THE DETECTION OF 'CANDIDATUS LIBERIBACTER SOLANACEARUM' ON PLANT HOSTS AND INSECT VECTORS

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'*Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum*' (Lso) is a phloem-limited, Gram-negative, unculturable bacterium that is spread by psyllid insect vectors. Lso is associated with diseases in solanaceous crops in New Zealand and Americas and with diseases in apiaceous crops in Europe and North Africa. This study reports the comparison, characterization and validation of different DNA extraction procedures for the detection of Lso on host plants and insect vectors. As regards the host plant samples, four DNA extraction methods were assessed: CTAB and three different commercial kits for the DNA extraction on nine different types of plant material. The CTAB method, the NucleoMag[®] Plant kit and the NucleoSpin[®] Food kit (Macherey-Nagel) provided the best universality as they were able to detect Lso on all the tested matrixes and gave the best analytical sensitivity with most of the matrixes. As for the insect vectors, three DNA extraction methods were assessed for DNA extraction. All the tested DNA extraction methods allowed the detection of Lso in the vector and the identification of the psyllid species.